

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Okello**FIRST NAME:** Richard**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your five key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12-14)

EXPECTATIONS OF A GOOD EUCLID RESPONSE PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

Excited upon enrolling in a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Global Health and Health Systems program at Euclid University, I read the orientation email and got confused about what I needed to do to get up and running with the first course, ACA-401D. I started by logging in to my Course Management System (CMS) account and changed my first course's status to 'Started' to access it in my Learning Management System (LMS) account. An email from the course instructor, Dr. Kabiru Gulma, was a game-changer for me. I read the email and the two attachments, how to write a EUCLID response paper and checklist for Euclid response paper and found my way out into the course.

I quickly logged into my LMS account, opened the course ACA-401D, opened period one, and read the instructions. I then downloaded and read the assigned study materials: ACA-401D coursepack, which was revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, and watched the ACA-401D introductory tutorial video delivered by

Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and was mesmerised by what it takes to write a good response paper at Euclid University.

Chapter one of the coursepack provided a general overview of the basics of essay writing, explained the steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-14). The second chapter explained all the punctuations and their usage, gave examples, and differentiated between correct and incorrect punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16-23). The third chapter explains US English and UK English and the differences between them (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32). Chapter four of the Coursepack explained plagiarism, how to avoid it, how and when to cite and paraphrase, and how to insert footnotes using MS Word (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39).

In chapter five, Prof. Laurent and Dr. Kabiru explained what a style guide is, why a writer needs a particular Style guide, and what a Style guide constitutes (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-42). Chapter six of the Coursepack explained the Chicago Style and its specifications and gave examples (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 43-57). Chapter seven explained standard Latin abbreviations used in writing, their meanings, and expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58-64). Chapter eight provided a sample of a response paper and showed how the Instructor notes feedback on it and the dos and don'ts of writing the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 65-71). Lastly, the ACA-401D introductory tutorial covered language, citation styles, and how to use paragraphs when writing response papers.

In this response paper, I will discuss five concepts that stood out in the assigned study materials: essay writing, punctuation, American vs. British English, plagiarism, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper.

2) EXPECTATIONS OF A GOOD RESPONSE PAPER AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

a) Writing a Good Academic Essay

Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024, 7). This definition is very informative. I now know that the response and major papers I will be writing in this course, as well as the subsequent ones, fall under this category and must meet the set standards. Prof. Laurent and Dr. Gulma stated, "Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to the other works, use of rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7). This is one area that I will focus on improving in this Doctorate of Philosophy (PhD) program.

Academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). In most cases, I

communicate ideas based on opinions rather than evidence. Therefore, the emphasis on evidence is one of the key takeaways from this course pack. One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). I find it challenging to improve my time management and organisation skills continuously; as Prof. Laurent and Dr. Gulma rightly put it, “It is never advisable to procrastinate” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

According to the Coursepack, while researching the topic, it is essential that the following questions are answered: What is already known about the subject? What needs to be read and known to write the essay? Is this valuable material for the topic/argument? Can the material be used to support the answer? The research can proceed if all the answers are ‘yes’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 8). I had never thought of these questions in all the studies that I have conducted. I was leaving out a crucial step of the research process, which I will adopt going forward.

Prof. Laurent and Dr. Gulma emphasised that essay writing requires creative and critical thinking.

The essay should include various information and viewpoints from different authors that explore a particular topic’s key arguments and relevant aspects. Do not only include evidence that agrees with what you are writing. If there are different or opposing views, they must be examined (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9).

I agree with the emphasis on acknowledging opposing views because it also sets the ground for the researcher to assert their argument.

“Essays get dramatically improved upon careful editing; check the overall structure of the essay, make sure each paragraph has a clear main point, and check transition signals.” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11-12). Having it all right in the first draft is nearly impossible. Continuous editing is one of the key takeaways from this course pack for me.

b) Punctuations

The coursepack emphasised using as few punctuations as possible while retaining the sentence’s meaning (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15). The use of several punctuations, including apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, full stops, exclamation marks, and quotation marks, are clearly explained, and several examples on how to apply them given (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23).

I benefited greatly from the explanations on using square brackets, *n-dash* and *m-dash*, and ellipsis because I had no idea of their use. Prof. Laurent and Dr. Gulma stated:

Square brackets are used to enclose comments, corrections, or translations made by a subsequent author or editor; n-dash is used in place of round brackets or commas, surrounded by spaces, and do not use m-dash; ellipsis is used to show that some text is

missing, usually from a quotation, and should not be surrounded with spaces (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 17, 20, 22).

These are concepts that I will adopt in my writings in the future.

c) American English vs. British English

Having studied through the British system and my Country, Uganda, a former colony of Britain, I am more familiar with British English than the US. The explanations in the Coursepack have made me discover several differences in spellings, pronunciations, and meanings of the exact words, and there are many similarities between the two English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32).

I have been using the two English words interchangeably in my writings, especially in spelling words, grammar, syntax, and general usage, an area I will focus on improving in the future. Since it is unacceptable to use the two English interchangeably at Euclid, I will stick to the British one that I am familiar with but also have sufficient knowledge of American English.

d) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). Prof. Laurent and Dr. Gulma emphasised that one must credit the author when using quotes, paraphrases, statistics/data, or visuals borrowed from another source (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024, 34). I have learned that I have been unknowingly committing two forms of plagiarism: paraphrasing and using visuals without acknowledging the authors, an area I will focus on improving from now on.

From the Coursepack, I have also learned that plagiarism is wrong, unethical, unfair, and a serious academic offence with serious consequences (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). I will start exercising caution in all my essays. Prof. Laurent and Dr. Kabiru stated:

Your paraphrase must look very different from how the author initially put it. It must be YOUR own words, the writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used, the information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote, and you must CITE the work information came from (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 36).

This is a fundamental concept that I have learned from this course pack. I used to write the sentences as they appeared in the original text and add in-text citations, thinking I was not committing plagiarism. Now I know that those sentences should have been quotes.

e) Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper

I have learned to follow the rules of thumb when writing a paper. Some of these rules include stating the central thesis in the opening paragraph, staying focused, not leading with sweeping generalities, writing clearly, making the writing enjoyable to the reader and not clumsy, supporting assertions, taking the views that I am addressing seriously, and avoiding committing plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11-14). These rules will make my papers credible, motivating to read, and in line with the ethics of writing.

3) CONCLUSION

When I first read about Euclid University, I developed very high expectations of its quality of education and decided that I must continue my studies there. This inaugural Coursepack confirmed my expectations. I have learned many concepts that will significantly improve my writing skills.

The use of punctuation like the square brackets, *n-dash*, and ellipsis are some things I had never had before. Even though all my writings from the start of school to date were in British English, I have learned that there are many things that I need to improve on, for example, spelling of words, grammar, syntax, and general usage.

When writing my master's degree dissertation, I focused on avoiding plagiarism. From the coursepack, I have learned that I was not paraphrasing correctly, which is also considered plagiarism. I was only exposed to the APA citation style, but now I understand the Turabian style required at Euclid University. I admire the rules of thumb explained in the Coursepack and intend to adopt them in my papers. The ACA-401D tutorial video by Prof. Laurent was very informative, and the demonstrations made it much easier to understand some of the concepts in the Coursepack.

The coursepack has challenged me to read more about the concepts I learned. I also intend to start practising essay writing while applying the concepts and tracking my progress in writing fluency.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.